

Survival Practices and Business Economic Goal Attainment among Table Water Producing Firms in Port Harcourt, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated survival practices and business economic goal attainment table water producing firms (TWPFs) in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. Using the cross correlational survey design, a population of 200 respondents drawn from three TWPFs. Data was collected with questionnaire and interpreted using the modified Likert 5-point descriptive tool while four hypotheses on four dimensions of survival practices (strategic planning, product innovation, value analysis and engineering and proactive customization) were formulated were tested against business economic goal attainment using the Product Moment Correlation Coefficient statistical tool and their output reported using the SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences). Our findings revealed all of the survival practices except proactive customization as a survival practice has significant relationship with business economic goal attainment and highly and positively correlated. Based on the findings, we conclude that these practices become strategic survival strategies upon which recommendations are made.

INTRODUCTION

Organizations operates in an unpredictable and dynamic environment with diverse changes. These diverse changes manifest in different forms and ranges from customers changing taste and preferences government policies and programmes that impact on the business. These changes are of great risks to manufacturing firms that have to deal with fast-changing markets feature both at high-level competition and numerous uncertainties in an unstable environment which affect the production at an uncompromising price levels for their survival and sustainability (Samuel, 2025; Heni et al., 2022). In particular, table water producing firms (TWPFs) as small and medium enterprises are always in search of new ways and means of enhancing their core competencies and capabilities for survival. Hence, survival of TWPFs and their attendant strategies are seen not as a game, but a war which they fight by deploying all sorts of business arsenal at their reach (Pollyn & Doobie, 2019). These arsenals so deployed enable these SMEs analyze, build, and reconfigure their resources and organizational capabilities in order to achieve flexibility and agility. Also of note is the increasing product and service dynamics and complexities which TWPFs contend with coupled

with market dynamism has also forced the adoption of all sorts of survival strategies and practices to ensure the survival and sustainability (Gerald et al., 2020; Rannikko et al., 2019)

It is also important to state that in a critically uncompromising RUDE (Rapidly Changing: Uncertain: Dynamic and Engaging) environment like the Nigeria manufacturing climate, most TWPFs struggle to meet up the environmental challenges thus run at loss. While some grow at snail speed, 80% of them dies before their fifth year of operation leaving only 20% of them to survive the shock of the RUDE and uncompromising environment (Obi et al., 2018; UNIDO ITPO, 2017; Osamwonyi & Tafamei, 2010; Oseni & Oseni, 2015; Akinbogun 2008). It goes to say that TWPFs in Nigeria in a bid to survive adopt various survival strategies ranging from unwholesome practices to acceptable survival practices of direct marketing, downsizing, owner or owner-family-member management, cost minimization etc. (Eneh 2010; Eze 1999). Worthy of note is that most of the unwholesome survival strategies adopted by TWPFs in Nigeria is carried out in connivance with government regulatory agencies and their officials since that have been the way out for their existence. Thus, this method of survival affects regulatory competence of the agencies of government to protect property rights and ensure the creation of wealth (Utomi, 2008).

It is therefore the direction of this study that survival strategies are required of TWPFs and by adopting established survival practices, they can confront the various RUDE challenges facing them in order to ensure that their occurrence does not affect their business operation negatively and also positioning them to achieve their desired level of competitiveness and sustainability goals (Pollyn and Doobie, 2019; Srinivasan et al., 2005; Liu & Heino, 2013). By embracing established survival strategies, TWPFs can direct effort and resources towards achieving the economic value goals of profitability, value creation, return on investment, economic value added etc. The adoption of TWPFs-fit survival strategy can go a long way to determine the resiliency and adaptation of each M TWPFs to the dynamics of the market and industry they serve (Grant & Ashford, 2008). It follows from the foregoing that TWPFs failures arise as a result of operators/ entrepreneurs failing to adopt TWPFs-fit survival strategies and practices which would positioned them to deal with the changing environment thus putting the such TWPFs in the positive path towards achieving desired level of sustained competitiveness.

It is also important to point that the attainment of business economic goals does not just happen; they are triggered by careful analysis and adoption of appropriate managerial and strategic options. As managerial option, survival strategies stems from the need for TWPFs to successful achieve economic goals in an unstable environment both in the short and long term of their existence. Therefore, TWPFs economic goals of profit maximization, revenue maximization, higher market

share, economic value added, wealth and value creation, balance growth rate etc. are achievable through the adoption of organization-fit survival strategy. Thus, by adopting relevant survival strategies, managers in the table water manufacturing subsector can plan ahead, develop innovative products and channels of reaching consumers in addition to coordinating people to learn and gain new insights of objective attainment.

Therefore, this study examined the contributory effect of survival practices and the attainment of business economic objectives among table water manufacturing firms in Port Harcourt, Nigeria using C-way Nigeria Limited and La Sien Bottling Company Limited considering the fact that many table water producing firms as Ololo water, TK water, Wonder water, Beulah water, Bliss water etc. came into the market in their numbers in Port Harcourt and also went out of business and market in their numbers not been able to compete favorably with such established table water like Eva, C-Way, Swam, Nestle etc. The benefits of the adoption of survival strategies by managers as discussed in the foregoing is generally to ensure that firms are not put in a “rat race” position to achieve their objectives but in a dominant position in the industry they serve leading to organizational stability and competitiveness. It follows that the non-adoption of relevant and durable strategies by managers for the strategic and creative management of TWPFs has often led to unethical business practices like “accounts padding” leading to tax evasion, expense account misrepresentation, incomplete disclosures to government and other stakeholders by management, connivance with government regulatory officers to produce substandard products/ product adulteration, unfair competition and unfair employment practices like staff casualization, outsourcing and unfair dismissals. It follows that when managers of TWPFs fail to adopt and apply relevant survival strategies, it puts the organization under undue stress, strained business operations resulting to business losses, loss of competitive advantage and stunted growth which in turn affect attainment of growth, profitability, competitive and sustainability objectives (Davis, 2016).

This study therefore proposes that by adopting organization-fit survival practices which in this study is taken to include value analysis and engineering, product innovation and strategic planning, managers of TWPFs can readily determine the path to follow, and win the business war towards the attainment of desired economic goals.

From the foregoing discussion, the study sought to identify the contributory influence of:

1. Strategic planning practices on business economic goal attainment among TWPFs in Port Harcourt.
2. Product innovation practices on business economic goal attainment among TWPFs in Port Harcourt.

3. Value analysis and engineering practices on business economic goal attainment among TWPFs in Port Harcourt.
4. Proactive customization practices on business economic goal attainment among TWPFs in Port Harcourt

Thus, we hypothesize that:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between strategic planning practices and business economic goal attainment among TWPFs in Port Harcourt.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between product innovation practices and business economic goal attainment among TWPFs in Port Harcourt.

H₀₃: Value analysis and engineering practices does not significantly contribute to economic goals attainment among TWPFs in Port Harcourt.

H₀₄: Proactive customization practices does not significantly contribute to economic goals attainment among TWPFs in Port Harcourt.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptualized Variables

Source: Researchers' Desktop Research, 2025

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Business Survival Practices

Business have remained agents of growth and sustainable economic development in Nigeria (Okon & Edet, 2016). Businesses in their various form constitute the bedrock of industrialization, employment generation and contribute over 75% of the gross domestic product of Nigeria economic development indices. However, it is reported by the Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN, 2004; SMEDAN/NBS, 2013) that 80% of startup and established businesses in Nigeria does not survive their first 5 years in business or struggle to achieve sustainable growth and profitability (Agwu & Emeti, 2014) coupled with lack of definite strategies to profitability run their business activities bearing in mind that the development and sustenance of business activities is of course every critical to the sustainability and rapid transformation of Nigeria to becoming one of the twenty largest economies in the world by 2020.

As a result of the plethora of challenges and pressures faced by businesses in Nigeria from an uncompromising RUDE environment they operate, critical survival strategies necessary to run and guide the day-to-day operations of TWPFs has become vital as they strive to realize their planned level of competitiveness. TWPFs as primary targets of an epileptic RUDE environment, adopt proactive survival strategies for deciding their business direction and sustainability. The survival strategy so adopted creates time and events consciousness in managers and makes them take strategic lead through effective knowledge management. It also makes managers not to wait for business success to come to them, but rather deal with expected challenges in advance (Aspinwall and Taylor, 1997). It brings about forward thinking intention for achieving sustainable business objectives while taking essential measures to mitigate inherent risk (Bindl & Parker, 2010; Thomas et al., 2010).

Survival Practices of Table Water Producing Firms

The following measures are conceptualized as necessary survival strategies by businesses in the table water operating environment.

A. Strategic Planning Practices

Planning is a major activity of managers and a variety of planning techniques are adopted to achieve organizational objectives. One of such technique is strategic planning. First, planning is the managerial process of deciding in advance what is to be done and how it is to be done (Terry, 2014). Planning therefore involves the formation of organizational objectives, formulation, evaluation and the selection of appropriate policies, strategies tactics and actions required to achieve the objectives which Sado (2014) note is a general process of determining organizational

objectives or goals and the best means an objective can effectively be attained. Hence, the very purpose of planning is to ease the accomplishment of organizational objectives in a most efficient manner to reduce business risks. Thus, strategic planning is a management activity for setting priorities, directing energy, achieving effective resource allocation, strengthening operations, and alignment of employees and other organizational stakeholders towards the attainment of common goals. It ensures organizations intended outcomes/ results (output) exceeds the inputs and serves as a control mechanism for guiding the execution of corporate strategies by bringing together the competence and skills of all managers to confront problems facing the organization. Thus effective strategic planning reduces uncertainty by anticipating and mitigating risk (Bryson et al., 2018; Nzewi, et al., 2017; Miller & Cardinal, 2017).

B. Product Innovation Practice

Organizations are known by their products or services delivered timely to their consumers and customers. To gain an edge over competitors, there is need for innovativeness of all organizational people whether managers or subordinates. In line with this reasoning, Jobber, David, Ellis-Chadwick and Fiona (2013), argue that product innovation deals with improvement of an old product, conception and development of new products, changes in design of established product, or use of new materials or components in the creation of conceptualized products. Product innovation includes introduction of new products, enhancing or rebranding old product quality, improving overall product performance, radical innovation (developing a totally new product) and incremental innovation that aimed at existing products in line with marketing trends.

C. Value Analysis and Engineering Practice

With an ever rising cost of doing business on the increase in Nigeria and consumers preference for cheaper goods and services, TWPFs are faced with dilemma of finding formal means of cutting cost of production in order to achieve profitability objective. When faced with such situation, one survival and profitability strategy that startups and established TWPFs can adopt and continuously apply in their effort to survive and remain in business is to adopt formal and recognizable cost reduction strategy as value analysis which when backed up with financial discipline is capable of generating desired sustainable goals. Value in this context is the ratio of function to cost which can be attained by either improving their products, functions and services with cost reduction and control towards profitability as the main focus. CIMA and Avis (2009), notes that value analysis is a “cost savings technique adopted by businesses to reduce the various inherent costs associated with a product or service without losing either use value or esteem value. It is a systematic inter-disciplinary examination of factors affecting the cost of a product or service, in order to

devise means of achieving the specified purpose most economically at the required standard of quality and reliability”. As a cost saving technique, it is a planned scientific approach to cost reduction which reviews the material composition of a product and production design so that modifications and improvements can be made which do not reduce the value of the product or service to the customer or to the user (Nixon et al., 1997; Whittle, n.d). in line with this, the Society of American Value Engineers (SAVE, 1963) states that “value analysis is the systematic application of recognized techniques which identify the function of a product or services and establish a monetary value for the function and provide the necessary function reliability at that lowest overall cost” while Miles and Buese (1957) described it as “the study of the relationship of design, function and cost of any material or service with the objective of reducing its cost through modification of design or material specifications, manufacture by more efficient process, changes in sources of supply, elimination or incorporation into another item.”

By adopting a continuous value analysis and engineering practice (systematic and critical assessment of every feature (materials, human element, and processes involved in a product of service as a survival strategy, TWPFs can systematically identify and selects the best value alternatives for designs, materials (from need identification to production or use), processes, and systems which answers such question as can the cost of an item, service or step be reduced or eliminated without diminishing the effectiveness, required quality for customers satisfaction towards profitability (Pollyn & Onwuchekwa, 2018).

Proactive Customization

One striking feature of TWPFs is their ability to get closer to their customers and getting to know them through the changing nature of their taste, needs, desires and consumption pattern have they practice proactive customization by linking their operation and products and services to each individual customer’s requirements and/or specifications. Understanding that customers are the focal point of their existence, TWPFs carryover market mapping, forecasting and most times personal selling as proactive measures to cater for customer’s needs. This involves providing low-cost, high-quality products and service, effective service delivery, and on-time delivery. TWPFs thus adopt know your customers’ strategy which helps them to intimately at all levels in the organization cater for the specific business needs at each level (Soltani et al., 2018; Olowokudejo & Adeleke, 2011).

It follows therefore that effective customer service is at the core of successful business enterprise especially TWPFs s. This is because attracting customers may not be a difficult task for TWPFs but how to retain them is the albatross because most of them are not generally ready to spent focused

costs or have considerable spending plans in advertising and other promotional activities geared towards achieving effective customer relations. TWPFs by and large derive their existence through attracting customers and working harder to hold their attention. Having a little rundown of customers should allow TWPFs to dedicate more opportunity to everyone, becoming more acquainted with them and their individual necessities. However, to some TWPFs, every customer, or for that matter every assignment is a priority because their ability to get new customers is often limited due to their size and resources. It is precisely because of this, that contrary to the general perception, TWPFs have and should have an edge when it comes to customer service to attract and retain their customers.

Businesses Economic Goals

A business is an economic unit which combines the various factors of production or economic-inputs toward the attainment of an economic objective. It therefore holds true that every business whether in their startup period or in their later years of existence have various economic objectives they work to achieve. The economic goals are the end-products of the difference between their orchestrated resource inputs and positive output achieved over a specific period of time (Pollyn & Doobie, 2019). It is also the ability of a business or a firm to achieve economic prosperity, producers surplus, profitability and desired customers base that generate its desired revenue and profit outcomes. While various measures are used in the measurement of objectives attained, this study relies on measures advocated by (Pandy, 2011) as follows.

1. Return on Investment (ROI)

Return on investment is a measure of gains or losses generated by an investment in relation to the amount of money invested therein. It is usually expressed as a percentage and is normally used for analyzing financial decisions and comparing a company's profitability or efficiency of different investments portfolios which a firm utilizes in generating profit. Also known as the accounting rate of return, Pandey (2005) note that RoI is a financial analysis tool used to determine the profitability or otherwise of investment portfolios. It may as well be referred to as the total or net assets ratio that indicates to managers how a firm is really performing, and how managers can use it as action plans to improve business performance (Brigham, 1995).

2. Profit Maximization

Profitability as a performance measurement standard assesses the economic added value of firms. It measures the return of a firm in relation to either sales or shareholders' equity which are usually calculated in percentage. It measures the operating efficiency organisations and show how effective

management has been in utilizing the resources of a firm. Profitability indicates the extent to which a firm generates profit from the application of its factors of production. Soteriou and Zenios (1999) advocated that profitability and its analysis focuses on the correlation between revenues generated and expense outlays and levels of desired profits achieved relative to the size of investments in the business determined through the use of profitability ratios (group of ratios which shows the combined effect of liquidity, assets management and debt management on operating results). Commonly used measures of profitability ratios are profit margin on sales, return on common equity (ROE), basic earning power (BEP), and return on total assets (ROA). By monitoring a firm's profitability levels, managers can measure business financial performance in a given year period.

3. Economic Value Creation

Value creation is the essence and foundation of successful businesses. It is one of the major indices that defines the direction of a business and used to measure the performance of a business. It is the starting point of business success story and the driving force of businesses to create and deliver value in an efficient manner towards profitability. It follows that value is an indispensable, desirable and trans-situational goals which businesses must pursue that varies in importance and serve as guiding business principle (Schwartz, 2012). Economic value is thus a measure of the benefit provided by a good or service to customers and is created when the business and its customers willingly enter into mutually beneficial transactions of giving and obtaining value (Public and Kolakovic, 2005). The mutually beneficial transactions that help in creating value become the building blocks of the free market system (Argandona, 1998). From the foregoing, economic value is created by businesses from a wide range of interactions, activities, relationships, causes and effects such as pricing strategy and operational efficiency (Moussaoui, 2017), brand equity (Krishna, 2015) and cost of capital. other drivers of economic value creation include but not limited to customer relations (Tate and Bals, 2016), societal expectations, environmental concerns (Smida and Sakal, 2014) innovation and corporate governance values such as integrity, trust and teamwork that support value creation (Isaksson, 2012). Economic value is also created when the price of that consumers pay for the goods and services is greater than the cost of production. Thus the economic value derived by the business is the cumulative difference between the consumer surplus (the difference the highest price that consumers are willing to pay for goods and the actual paid) and the producer surplus which is the difference between the price sellers actually sell their goods and services and the total cost of producing the goods or service consumed by the consumers.

4. Sales Revenue Maximization

Sales revenue in simple terms is the total cumulative number of units of a company product or service sold over a given period of time and multiplied by the price per unit of that product or service undertaken as part of the business core operating activities. Perfectly tracking sales revenue and the ability to effectively analyze the details has been an important ingredient of network marketing teams. This is because, accurate measurement of sales revenue is the foundation for making important decisions, setting the direction for marketing team success and calculation of trade points and commission. It is also used to determine the growth and hierarchy to be obtained by each team in the multiple-level marketing chart of each company which the team is operating thereto.

As a result of the foregoing importance of increase sales revenue to network marketing teams (NMTs), Rezvani et al, (2017), Yildiz and Yildiz, (2013) and Msweli-Mbanga (2001) noted that NMTs adopt different strategies towards achieving that goal which ranges from massive marketing campaigns to increase customer base, adoption of innovative entrepreneurial practices, attracting more independent retailers, creating sound B2C (business-to-customer) environment, proactive customization practices and regular training and retraining of team members through their network and clustered business training schools.

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Previous studies have justified why small businesses remain the engine of growth in an economy like Nigeria (Edet & Okon, 2018). Successful small businesses would facilitate the employment chain in the economy, and provide jobs for employees and the business owners, inputs for other firms, tax receipts for the government, products and services for the customers, and inputs for other concerns hence the need to discover survival techniques and reasons for its downfall. This section focuses on review of empirical literature related to the study proactive survival strategies and performance of micro, small and medium scale bakeries.

Paschal, Anyanwu and Eke (2017) studied survival strategies in a challenging environment: focus on maritime companies in Port Harcourt. The work amongst other things examined the relationship between survival strategies and maritime business growth; It as well ascertained the relationship between safety practice/ship turnaround time and growth and survival of a shipping line. To achieve the spelt objectives, the study utilized cross-sectional survey design; and data was collected though a self-administered questionnaire from a number of 52 respondents who were staff of selected maritime firms in Port Harcourt, River State, Nigeria. Statistical technique software SPSS was employed to aid the data analysis. Having analyzed the data, the study found

out that: survival strategies build maritime business growth. It was also discovered that growth and survival of a shipping line is dependent on the safety practice/ship turnaround time of maritime firms

Ifekwem and Adedamola (2016) revised survival strategies and sustainability of SMEs using selected small businesses in Oshodi-Isolo Local Government, Lagos State. Using the selected owners of small businesses in Oshodi-Isolo, Lagos State, as the population of interest, a survey research design was adopted in this study. 50 SMEs were randomly sampled and their owners and managers interviewed using a questionnaire. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistic and Pearson's product-moment correlation coefficient statistics was used to test the hypotheses with the aid of the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) Version 21.0. The study examined the type of growth strategies that SMEs adopts, ascertains what influences their survival strategies as well as the challenges that hinder their growth. Their findings revealed that there is a statistically significant relationship between survival strategies and SMEs' sustainability; they posited that maintaining small but committed and motivated employees is critical in guaranteeing the survival of the SMEs in a volatile economy

Iorun (2014) studied evaluation of survival strategies of small and medium enterprises in Benue State. The study adopted a quantitative research design. Under the quantitative design, survey research method was employed for the study. The study sampled 180 respondents from 30 small business enterprises using a random sampling technique. Primary data were applied in carrying out the research work. Chi square method was employed to analyze the data. The results reveal that creativity is a strategy for the survival of small business enterprises in Nigeria. The results also indicate that high risk taking is a strategy for the survival of SMEs in Nigeria. Lastly, the results also show that, areas of opportunities for business are a panacea for the survival of SMEs in Nigeria.

Aremu and Adeyemi (2011) studied small and medium scale enterprises as a survival strategy for employment generation in Nigeria. The study employed survey design. The study population comprised SMEs registered with Small and Medium Enterprise Development Agency of Nigeria in Lagos State with the total of 4,535. The Taro Yamane formula was used to obtain a sample size of 478. The owners/managers of these SMEs were selected through a multi-stage sampling technique which involves the stratified, proportionate, and simple random sampling method. The instrument validity was established through scrutiny and evaluation by the research supervisor and experts in the study area, and reliability was determined via Cronbach's alpha coefficient computed from pilot study responses. By the use of instrument codes, responses were processed into quantitative

data for descriptive and empirical analyses. Result revealed that infrastructural facilities have a significant and positive effect on SME's service quality ($R^2= 0.872$: $p= 0.000<0.05$). The government taxation policy has a significant and positive effect on sales revenue ($R^2= 0.896$: $p= 0.000<0.05$). On the government/institutional support variable, result shows that it has a positive but no significant influence on job creation ($R^2= 0.094$: $p= 0.879>0.05$). The analysis of insecurity and market growth shows a negative and significant effect of insecurity on SMEs market growth potentials ($R^2= 0.011$: $p= 0.036<0.05$). The paper concludes that besides the growth potential of the sector and its critical role in the manufacturing and value chains. Their wide spread in Nigeria and the multiplier effects they have on the rest of the economy enable them to be the engine of economic progress. It was also noted that the SME sector is the main driving force behind job creation, poverty reduction, wealth creation, income distribution and reduction in income disparities. Most of the government interventions failed to create a much needed transformation due to poor coordination and monitoring and policy inconsistencies.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The cross sectional correlational survey design was adopted for this study. It is adopted as it helped in the decomposition of survival practices, data generation and their interplay with business economic goals.

Target Population

The population of the study consisted of 200 top level managers, middle level managers and supervisory personnel of C-WAY Nigeria limited, La Sien Bottling Company Limited and Jossy Kings Associates (Nig. Ltd), Port Harcourt. The research instrument (the questionnaire) was proportionally distributed to the respondents in the three firms over a period of eight weeks and responses obtained.

Sample Size, Sampling Technique and Instrumentation

Since the population of the study consists of 200 respondents and is not large enough, the population sample size was adopted for the study. However, the modified proportional simple random technique was adopted in the administration of the questionnaire in the three organizations. Responses to each question relied on **on the modified Likert five (5) point scale** with weights of 5, 4, 3, 2, 1 attached to responses on relational work strategy and performance of network marketing teams. The responses were modified using: strongly agreed (SA5), agreed (AG4),

agreed to an extent (AA3), disagreed (DA2) and strongly disagreed (SD1). The test of hypotheses was done using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient is given as:

$$r = \frac{n(\sum xy) - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{\left[n\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2 \right] \left[n\sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2 \right]}}$$

Where:

- r = is the correlation value obtained at each point of analysis
- n = pairs of Likert scale responses (in this case pairs of 5)
- y = data related to non-decomposed **dependent variable** and;
- x = data related to each of the decomposed **independent variable** dimensions
- \sum = Summation (cumulative) sign

The output and outcome of the correlational findings between the variables and hypotheses testing based on the test of significance is achieved with the aid of the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.

DESCRIPTIVE RESULTS, HYPOTHESES TESTING AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Here we present the demographical details of respondents, tested the four hypotheses for drawing inferences and discuss findings from the empirical results.

Demographic Characteristics

Table 1: Questionnaire Administration and Retrieval from the selected firms

S/N	TWPF	No. Administered	No Retrieved	%
1.	C-Way	105	57	54.29
2.	Jossy King	50	27	54
3.	La Sien	45	24	53.33
	Total	200	108	-
	Average response			53.87

Source: Desktop Field Data, 2025

Table 2: Demographic Distribution

Qualification	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
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Gender	Male	64	59.26	59.26	59.26
	Female	44	40.74	40.74	100
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	
Staff Category					
	Senior Management	22	20.37	20.37	20.37
	Middle management	39	36.11	36.11	56.48
	Supervisors	47	43.52	43.52	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	
Education					
	SSCE	20	18.52	18.52	18.52
	OND	25	23.15	23.15	41.67
	HND/ BSc	39	36.11	36.11	77.78
	Postgraduate	24	22.22	22.22	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	
Age					
	18-35 years	26	24.08	24.08	24.08
	36-45 years	34	31.48	31.48	55.56
	46 years and above	48	44.44	44.44	100.0
	Total	108	100.00	100.00	
Experience					
	1- 5 years	35	32.40	32.40	32.30
	6-10 years	50	46.30	46.30	78.70
	11 years and above	23	21.30	21.30	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	

Source: SPSS Output from Desktop Field Data, 2025

Test of Hypotheses and Discussion of Empirical Findings

This study had proposed four survival practices (strategic planning practices, product innovation practices, value analysis and engineering practices and proactive customization practices) as the predictor variable and business economic goals (the criterion variables). The standard (α – alpha) significance level of 0.05 is adopted as cut-off or critical value to reject or retain (accept) the null hypothesis. If the significance level displayed by the SPSS output (that is, α – alpha calculated) is less than or equal to the critical value, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate accepted. In testing the hypotheses, the following rules was held. All coefficients of (r) values that indicate levels of significance (* or **) as calculated using SPSS were accepted and thus the hypotheses were accepted and when no significance is indicated in the coefficient (p or r) value, the null hypotheses were rejected. Hence, both significance values and coefficient values were applied in drawing inferences in this study.

Test of Hypotheses One

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between strategic planning practices and business economic goal attainment among TWPFs in Port Harcourt.

Table 3: Correlations between strategic planning and business economic goal attainment and its dimensions

		Strategic planning	Economic goal attainment	Economic value creation	Profit maximi- zation	Return on Investment	Sales Revenue Maximi-za- tion	Wealth maximi-za- tion
Strategic planning	Pearson	1	.930*	.330	.677	.383	.556	.950*
	Correlation							
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.022	.588	.210	.524	.331	.013
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Economic goal attainment	Pearson	.930*	1	.651	.742	.576	.715	.818
	Correlation							
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.022		.235	.151	.310	.175	.090
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Economic value creation	Pearson	.330	.651	1	.579	.769	.774	.157
	Correlation							
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.588	.235		.306	.128	.124	.801
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Profit maximization	Pearson	.677	.742	.579	1	.573	.902*	.730
	Correlation							
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.210	.151	.306		.312	.036	.161
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Return on Investment	Pearson	.383	.576	.769	.573	1	.865	.199
	Correlation							
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.524	.310	.128	.312		.058	.748
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Sales Revenue Max	Pearson	.556	.715	.774	.902*	.865	1	.497
	Correlation							
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.331	.175	.124	.036	.058		.394
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Wealth maximization	Pearson	.950*	.818	.157	.730	.199	.497	1
	Correlation							
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.013	.090	.801	.161	.748	.394	
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Correlation coefficient values and test of significance values for hypothesis one as shown in the table above showed that with a p-value of .930 between strategic planning and business economic goal attainment, there is a high and positive correlation between the variables and with a significance value of .022 which is less than the critical (α – alpha) significance value of 0.05, the null hypothesis (Ho) is rejected and alternate hypothesis accepted which implies that there is significant relationship between strategic planning practices and business economic goal attainment among TWPFs in Port Harcourt. In specific terms, analysis of the sub-variables of business economic goals (economic value creation, profit maximization, return on investment, sales revenue maximization and wealth maximization) revealed that strategic planning practices do not influence all but wealth maximization. Economic value creation (.588), profit maximization (.210), return on investment (.524), sales revenue maximization (.331) are not influenced by strategic planning and wealth maximization (.013) is influenced by strategic planning practices. Further to this, analysis showed that economic value creation with a p-value of .330 indicated low

but positive correlation, profit maximization (ρ -value = .677) indicates high and positive correlation. Return on investment (ρ -value = .383) showed low but positive correlation, sales revenue maximization (ρ -value = .556); high but positive correlation and wealth maximization (ρ -value = .950) very high correlation.

Test of Hypotheses Two

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between product innovation practices and business economic goal attainment among TWPFs in Port Harcourt.

Table 4: Correlations between product innovation practices and economic goal attainment and its dimensions

		Product innovation	Economic goal attainment	Economic value creation	Profit maximization	Return on Investment	Sales Revenue Maximization	Wealth maximization
Product innovation	Pearson Correlation	1	.927*	-.505	-.578	.452	.968**	.416
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.023	.385	.308	.445	.007	.486
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Economic goal attainment	Pearson Correlation	.927*	1	-.265	-.517	.655	.947*	.671
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.023		.666	.372	.230	.014	.215
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Economic value creation	Pearson Correlation	-.505	-.265	1	-.079	.265	-.277	.319
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.385	.666		.900	.667	.652	.600
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Profit maximization	Pearson Correlation	-.578	-.517	-.079	1	-.033	-.657	-.570
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.308	.372	.900		.958	.228	.316
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Return on Investment	Pearson Correlation	.452	.655	.265	-.033	1	.589	.430
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.445	.230	.667	.958		.296	.470
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Sales Revenue Max	Pearson Correlation	.968**	.947*	-.277	-.657	.589	1	.524
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.007	.014	.652	.228	.296		.365
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Wealth maximization	Pearson Correlation	.416	.671	.319	-.570	.430	.524	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.486	.215	.600	.316	.470	.365	
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Correlation coefficient values and test of significance values for hypothesis two as shown in table 4 indicated that with a p-value of .927 between product innovation practices and business economic

goal attainment, there is a high and positive correlation between the variables and with a significance value of .023 which is less than the critical (α – alpha) value of 0.05, the null hypothesis (Ho) is rejected and alternate hypothesis accepted. It implies that there is significant relationship between product innovation practices and business economic goal attainment among TWPFs in Port Harcourt. In specific terms, analysis of the sub-variables of business economic goals (economic value creation, profit maximization, return on investment, sales revenue maximization and wealth maximization) revealed that product innovation practices do not influence all but of sales revenue maximization. Economic value creation (.385), profit maximization (.308), return on investment (.445) and wealth maximization (.486) are not influenced by product innovation. However, sales revenue maximization (.007) is influenced by product innovation practices. Further to this, analysis showed that economic value creation with a ρ -value of -.505 and profit maximization (ρ -value = -.578) indicated moderate and negative correlation while return on investment (ρ -value = .452) and wealth maximization (ρ -value = .416) showed low but positive correlation respectively. Further to this, with (ρ -value = .968), product innovation practices has a very high and positive correlation with sales revenue maximization.

Test of Hypotheses Three

H₀₃: Value analysis and engineering practices does not significantly contribute to economic goals attainment among TWPFs in Port Harcourt.

Table 5: Correlations between value analysis and engineering practices and business economic goal attainment and its dimensions

		Value analysis & engineering	Economic goal attainment	Economic value creation	Profit maximization	Return on Investment	Sales Revenue Maximization	Wealth maximization
Value analysis & engineering	Pearson Correlation	1	.969**	.330	.677	.383	.556	.950*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.006	.588	.210	.524	.331	.013
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Economic goal attainment	Pearson Correlation	.969**	1	.282	.715	.486	.631	.929*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.006		.645	.175	.406	.254	.022
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Economic value creation	Pearson Correlation	.330	.282	1	.579	.769	.774	.157
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.588	.645		.306	.128	.124	.801
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Profit maximization	Pearson Correlation	.677	.715	.579	1	.573	.902*	.730
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.210	.175	.306		.312	.036	.161
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

Return on Investment	Pearson Correlation	.383	.486	.769	.573	1	.865	.199
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.524	.406	.128	.312		.058	.748
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Sales Revenue Maximization	Pearson Correlation	.556	.631	.774	.902*	.865	1	.497
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.331	.254	.124	.036	.058		.394
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Wealth maximization	Pearson Correlation	.950*	.929*	.157	.730	.199	.497	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.013	.022	.801	.161	.748	.394	
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Correlation coefficient values and test of significance values for hypothesis three shown in table 5 indicated that with a p-value of .969 between value analysis and engineering practices and business economic goal attainment, there is very high and positive correlation between the variables and with a significance value of .006 which is less than the critical (α – alpha) value of 0.05, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected and alternate hypothesis accepted. It implies that there is significant relationship between value analysis and engineering practices and business economic goal attainment among TWPFs in Port Harcourt. In specific terms, analysis of the sub-variables of business economic goals (economic value creation, profit maximization, return on investment, sales revenue maximization and wealth maximization) revealed that value analysis and engineering practices do not influence all but wealth maximization (.013). Economic value creation (.588), profit maximization (.210), return on investment (.524) and sales revenue maximization (.331) are not influenced by product innovation. Further analysis revealed that economic value creation (ρ -value = .330) and return on investments (ρ -value = .330) lowly but positively correlated with value analysis and engineering practices while profit maximization (ρ -value = .677) and sales revenue maximization (ρ -value = .556) are highly and positively correlated with value analysis and engineering practices respectively. Further to this, wealth maximization (ρ -value = .950) is highly and positively correlated with value analysis and engineering practices.

Test of Hypotheses Four

H_{04} : Proactive customization practices does not significantly contribute to economic goals attainment among TWPFs in Port Harcourt.

Table 6: Correlations between proactive customization practices and business economic goal attainment and its dimensions

		Proactive customization	Economic goal attainment	Economic value creation	Profit maximization	Return on Investment	Sales Revenue Maximization	Wealth maximization
Proactive customization	Pearson Correlation	1	.643	.637	.177	.698	.514	.574
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.242	.248	.776	.190	.376	.311
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Economic goal attainment	Pearson Correlation	.643	1	.563	.726	.836	.906*	.906*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.242		.323	.165	.078	.034	.034
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Economic value creation	Pearson Correlation	.637	.563	1	.004	.174	.620	.191
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.248	.323		.995	.779	.265	.758
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Profit maximization	Pearson Correlation	.177	.726	.004	1	.748	.458	.811
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.776	.165	.995		.146	.438	.096
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Return on Investment	Pearson Correlation	.698	.836	.174	.748	1	.611	.966**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.190	.078	.779	.146		.274	.008
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Sales Revenue Maximization	Pearson Correlation	.514	.906*	.620	.458	.611	1	.744
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.376	.034	.265	.438	.274		.149
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Wealth maximization	Pearson Correlation	.574	.906*	.191	.811	.966**	.744	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.311	.034	.758	.096	.008	.149	
	N	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Test of hypothesis four and its analysis in table 6 indicates that with a p-value of .643 between proactive customization practices and business economic goal attainment, there is very high and positive correlation between the variables and with a significance value of .242 which is greater than the critical (α – alpha) value of 0.05, the null hypothesis (Ho) is retained. In specific terms, analysis of the sub-variables of business economic goals (economic value creation, profit maximization, return on investment, sales revenue maximization and wealth maximization) relative proactive customization practices revealed that it does not influence all of the sub-variables. Further analysis revealed that all of the sub-variables except profit maximization (p-value = .177) is lowly but positively correlated with proactive customization practices.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study had examined survival practices and business economic goal attainment among TWPFs in Port Harcourt. Empirical findings from the study revealed that:

1. There is significant relationship strategic planning practices and business economic goal attainment among TWPFs in Port Harcourt.
2. There is significant relationship between product innovation practices and business economic goal attainment among TWPFs in Port Harcourt
3. Value analysis and engineering practices significantly influences business economic goal attainment among TWPFs in Port Harcourt.
4. Proactive customization practices do not significantly influence business economic goal attainment among TWPFs in Port Harcourt

Conclusively, it follows that strategic planning, product innovation coupled with value analysis and engineering practices when adopted as survival practices can be totally deployed as survival strategies and become necessary means and strategic tool for achieving competitiveness and performance while proactive customization practices should be considered side-by-side with these practices to attract customers since production and marketing of table water cannot be attained in a vacuum but with customers who are ‘kings’ that determine the survival, sustainability and competitiveness of firms. It thus, becomes imperative to conclude that survival strategies are effective managerial actions and business plans that can be likened to the biblical ‘Stone of David’ capable of killing all challenges that confront businesses and if overlooked can lead to business failures. It follows that when an effective survival strategy in place, TWPFs will not only adaptive but also be forward looking which will help in reducing business paralysis, cost minimization and effective utilization of scare resources for optimum performance.

In the light of the above findings and conclusions, it is recommended that:

1. Strategic planning should be a holistic, integrative, conscious and continuous activity that must be the foundation for mapping survival strategies and their implementation.
2. Value analysis and engineering practices should be the centre piece of the survival strategies for effectively reducing cost achieving profitability among TWPFs since these are the key critical success factors of production firms.
3. To achieve product innovation practices, sound market mapping strategies capable of identifying market dynamics and consumer changing should be adopted as a strategic business focus as it is capable of generating forward thinking strategies. The tenets of

product innovative teams should be adopted by table water producing firms as a necessity for effective research, conceptualization, development and marketing by TWPFs.

4. Proactive customization practices should be considered side-by-side with other practices and enhanced since innovative production and marketing of table water products cannot be attained in a vacuum.

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